

Alternate crops for an upland rice-based cropping system in Karnataka

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Drought in recent years has caused very low rice yields (around 1 t/ha), leading to low income for farmers in upland rice areas. We evaluated 12 alternative low water-requiring crops and rice varieties Champakali and Rasi for yield potential and return during the 1987-89 wet seasons.

The field experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Practices recommended for the transitional area (a narrow strip at 400-900 m elevation with 620-1300 mm annual rainfall) were followed.

Total precipitation during the cropping seasons was 738 mm in 1987, 1034 mm in 1988, and 607 mm in 1989. Rainfall early in the 1987 and 1989 seasons was far below average, leading to lower rice yields (see table). In those years, hybrid maize gave the highest mean yield,

Yield and gross returns from crops in a rainfed upland rice system. Mugad, Karnataka, India, 1987-89.

Crop	Mean of 1987 and 1989		Mean of 1987, 1988, and 1989	
	Yield (t/ha)	Return (\$/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Return (\$/ha)
Ragi	3.3	373	2.2	248
Green gram	0.6	242	0.4	161
Niger	0.5	196	0.3	131
Groundnut	2.0	791	1.4	527
Soybean	0.7	171	0.4	114
Black soya	0.6	161	0.4	107
Cowpea	0.4	123	0.3	82
Sunflower	0.4	111	0.3	74
Red gram	1.4	391	0.9	261
Hybrid maize	4.5	565	3.0	376
Castor	0.7	324	0.5	216
Hybrid cotton (DCH-32)	1.4	694	0.9	463
Cotton (DB-3-12)	0.5	238	0.5	238
Rice (Champakali)	0.6	73	1.9	220
Rice (Rasi)	1.1	122	1.9	215

followed by ragi, groundnut, red gram, and hybrid cotton. Gross returns were highest for groundnut, followed by hybrid cotton, hybrid maize, red gram, and ragi.

In 1988, continuous heavy rainfall from Jun to Sep 1988 resulted in complete failure of all crops except rice. Average rice yield was 4.5 t/ha for

Champakali and 3.5 t/ha for Rasi.

Our conclusion is that other crops cannot always replace rice in the uplands, but there is scope to include other crops like hybrid maize, ragi, groundnut, red gram, and hybrid cotton in rice-based systems, to stabilize yield and income across seasons. ■

Rice-based cropping systems for irrigated ricelands

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We studied the effect of irrigation on the performance of wheat and mustard under zero tillage after drill sown and transplanted rice in 1989-90.

The soil was clay with pH 6.7, 0.64% organic C, and 17.3 kg available P₂O₅ and 148 kg available K₂O/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications.

Abhilash rice (150 d duration) was harvested 7 Dec 1989. HD-2189 wheat (115 d duration) was sown in 20-cm rows and Sita mustard (85 d duration) was sown in 40-cm rows on 29 Dec.

Production potential of irrigated wheat and mustard after irrigated rice. Karnataka, India, 1989-90.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Net profit (\$/ha)	Benefit-to-cost ratio
	Wheat	Mustard		
<i>Rice planting method</i>				
Drill seeding	2.2	0.6	270	3.02
Transplanting	2.2	0.4	208	2.64
<i>Irrigation level</i>				
At seeding and flowering	1.7	0.5	170	2.30
At seeding, flowering, and grain filling	2.2	0.5	222	2.71
At seeding, vegetative phase, flowering, and grain filling	2.9	0.6	325	3.47
<i>Average</i>				
Wheat			316	3.68
Mustard			162	1.97

Both crops received 50 kg N and 13 kg P/ha. Total precipitation during 1989-90 was very low (687.9 mm), which necessitated two common irrigations to all plots in the early vegetative phase, for crop establishment.

Wheat recorded the highest grain yield with irrigation at seeding, vegetative,

flowering, and grain filling stages. Skipping one irrigation at the vegetative phase reduced yield 23%; skipping irrigations at vegetative and at grain filling stages reduced yield 41% (see table). Mustard yields did not differ significantly with irrigation. Monetary returns were higher for wheat. ■